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RESEARCH ARTICLE

Last Will Letter: A Secure Federated P2P Scheme for Blockchain-Oriented Virtual Redundancy and Backup

CESAR A. CAZAL¹, (Graduate Student Member, IEEE),
SU MON TUN¹, (Graduate Student Member, IEEE), **LEONARDO LEONZI D'ALESSANDRO**²,
STEFAN LANKES¹, **FERDINANDA PONCI**¹, (Senior Member, IEEE),
AND ANTONELLO MONTI^{1,3}, (Senior Member, IEEE)

¹Institute for Automation of Complex Power Systems, E.ON Energy Research Center, RWTH Aachen University, 52074 Aachen, Germany

²TTCControl, 39042 Bolzano, Italy

³Fraunhofer Institute for Applied Information Technology (FIT), 52062 Aachen, Germany

Corresponding author: Cesar A. Cazal (cesar.cazal@eonerc.rwth-aachen.de)

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ABSTRACT This work extends previous research on blockchain-based Virtual Redundancy, proposing a new approach to improve the reliability of distributed systems, with a focus on power grid applications. The original solution used blockchain's fault-tolerant properties to provide redundancy through virtualization. However, the existing application layer and API proved unsuitable for future projects. Moreover, building on the original architecture and optimal machine allocation algorithm, this work introduces a peer-to-peer (P2P) alternative to replace the application layer and API. The design addresses three major security concerns in algorithm allocation: information leaks, malware propagation, and man-in-the-middle attacks. To mitigate these risks, a scheme called the Last Will Letter is proposed, which involves three types of nodes, the Testator, the Inheritor, and the Executor, modeled after a fictional succession ritual. The scheme presented in the current study has been deployed and tested on a five-node network under stress conditions, such as single-node failures. Results show the system maintains performance while enabling secure migration. Finally, execution times and computational requirements for achieving Virtual Redundancy with this scheme are also reported.

INDEX TERMS Last Will Letter, virtual redundancy, blockchain, secure migration, federated peer-to-peer, power grid, automation, fault tolerance.

I. INTRODUCTION

The adoption of new Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) for the automation of power systems also inherits the rising threats of cyber-attacks on the electric network to disrupt the normal operation of any society. This is the case observed in 2014, during the coordinated cyber-attacks carried over on the Ukrainian distribution network [1], exposing the vulnerabilities present

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in centralized automation techniques as Single Points of Failure (SPOF) in the system, in consequence, constituting the main targets for cyber warfare and criminal attacks. To this point, several countermeasures have been proposed to tackle cyber-physical attacks on power grids. Nevertheless, we will give special emphasis on the distributed architecture proposed in [2], as this work represents a continuation of the research initiated. Given the virtual character of the solution, where idle resources of collaborative machines are assigned to perform the task in the control of physical components in computational nodes, the solution was internally renamed as

FIGURE 1. Conventional redundancy vs. virtual redundancy concept representation. The algorithms (A1,A2,...,An) are executed inside every machine.

“Virtual Redundancy”, considering that the resources do not come to action until a failure is detected in the system, as it can be appreciated in 1.

In that approach, a blockchain-based architecture is proposed, centered in the Hyperledger Fabric framework to exploit the fail-proof characteristic of distributed solutions. Next, it runs a series of smart contracts for the creation, reading, and updating of the different actors and parameters that feed an algorithm for the selection of the optimal host machine of the local program. Once the optimal machine is selected, the information is transmitted to node-red, which acts as an interface between the smart contract and Calvin IoT. This last is a platform in charge of managing the local actor, communicating with the future host, and migrating the program in case the original machine can no longer respond in the system.

Unfortunately, the main component of the application layer, Calvin IoT, has fallen deprecated [3], bringing up the need for revision of the whole solution proposed by [2]. So, in this case, we took the opportunity to analyze in detail the solution proposed and identify possible improvement points by studying potential threats that might come together:

- **Malware propagation:** It is the spread of malicious programs along the network. The current solution does not provide isolation for the received files in case of the presence of malware nor prevent its propagation. This point can disrupt the operation of the new host machine or trigger a chain reaction within the network in case the malware gets “automatically migrated”.
- **Data Leak:** Defined as the exposure of confidential, sensitive, protected, or critical information to unauthorized parties. The solution presented in [2] does not protect the received program’s information from being accessed before the migration. In case the new host takes possession of the program migrated, he can disrupt the operation of the network by e.g. sending contradictory instructions to the physical devices, making use of the information within the program to disrupt other services with similar functions within the network, etc.
- **Man-in-the-middle attack:** Defined as an attack where a malicious actor secretly intercepts and (potentially) modifies the data exchanged between two other parties [4]. The solution proposed by [2] does not protect

the network in case the new host machine represents an infiltrated threat, putting itself between the processing software recently migrated, and the computer receiving the processed information. Here, in case the new host behaves maliciously, it can either report similar but dangerous values to create malfunctions in the system, or even take malign possession of the controlled physical end (for the case of power systems). These types of attacks can be hard to detect due to the use of privileged information.

- To overcome the limitations, and given the need to replace Calvin IoT, we proposed a new architecture for the application end to deal with these specific problems while preserving the rest of the solution intact, considering the contribution of transparency and fail-proof properties of the blockchain framework, including a first defensive wall: the need for certificates to participate in the system.

The main contributions of this document are the following:

- The study proposes a new framework to protect the new host machine in case of malware file propagation.
- A novel Federated Peer-to-Peer (P2P) Algorithm, where no actor involved gathers enough information about the migrated file until the original machine loses connection to the network.
- A consensus-mode operation for critical processes to verify the correct action of the new host machine(s).
- A Proof-of-Concept (PoC) of the proposed application developed in Node.js is presented and integrated into the Smart Contract and Blockchain Framework of the solution presented in [2].
- The working functionality of the overall system (i.e. migration process) of the implemented prototype is tested and the performance evaluation as well as the system response to normal and unfavorable conditions are presented.

II. THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

In this chapter, we revise the fundamentals necessary to understand and implement the proposed algorithm. It is important to add that the different elements presented within the chapter start with the current state of the art, and then we proceed to describe the different concepts necessary to understand the present solution. In the process, we expect to describe the characteristics and clarify the limitations of every technology presented, to properly comprehend the characteristics of the current solution.

A. REDUNDANCY FUNDAMENTALS

Before proceeding further, we need to speak about how redundant systems are commonly classified: as $N+1$, for a single redundant element, $N+2$, for two redundant elements, $2N$ for double of every element, and so on. For practical reasons, we will adopt “ $N+r$ ”, for “ r ” as the redundant number of elements within the system, which we will call

redundant value “r”, which we will use in several sections of this paper.

To this point, we have presented a redundant operation, where there is only one copy of the original program to be migrated, giving us a redundant factor of two (original node plus the redundant node). In case the redundant host fails before the original node, we would lose all redundancy in the system, leaving us with the need to revise the strategies to increase the chances of service availability upon failures within the system.

Here we would like to show the different possible strategies to be followed to preserve enough data for migration. If we consider the mean chances for one machine to fail in a defined period are λ , the reciprocal $\lambda - 1$ would be the Mean Time Between Failures (or MTBF, if we consider the failures are repairable). Nonetheless, the overall system failure for different components has a different behavior compared to the probabilities for two failure events to converge at the same time, as we can see in equation (1) [5]. If we assume the components are in their useful life period, and have a constant failure rate (i.e. only due to random failures), we can make some practical assumptions. In other words, even when two independent components of a bigger system might have the same failure rate, the chances that both machines fail simultaneously within the same period (defined by the Mean Time to Repair or “MTTR”) are a quadratic function, while three machines respond to a cubic function, and so on.

$$MTBF_{sys} = \frac{MTBF_1 \cdot MTBF_2 \cdot \dots \cdot MTBF_n}{MTTR_1 + MTTR_2 + \dots + MTTR_n} \quad (1)$$

In consequence, in the case of redundant information, the more copies of the data, the less the chances of losing it (exponentially better, so to say). To implement it there are different methods, but we should take a special look into two very relevant for us:

- **Data Replication:** This procedure consists of creating an entire number of copies of the data (independent of full or split) and distributing them to different storage units. This is the simplest way of creating redundancy, but it presents risks of lost data in the transport or storage process, as well as inefficiencies. For split files, what counts is the number of copies created of every piece.+
- **Rabin’s Information Dispersal Algorithm (IDA) [6]:** With this algorithm, we can split the file on “n” arbitrary pieces of length “L”, so just “m” (also arbitrary) pieces are enough to reconstruct the whole file. For this, the. Each of the “n” pieces has a length of $l=L/m$, where, when having “m” pieces we have enough information to reconstruct the whole file, making it more storage efficient than simple data replication and highly fault-tolerant.

In a simple analysis, if we take a file split into four pieces, with a redundant value of three, for the data replication scenario we would need a total of 12 equal-sized pieces totaling 3 times the storage need, while for the IDA case, for 12 pieces we only need “m” to be “n-3”, leaving us with

FIGURE 2. Symmetric key encryption scheme.

a total space needed of 1.33 times more than the original file, reducing in this way possible errors and the overall space required for having equal redundancy (we can have up to 3 failed components in the system). It is important to add that, as we assume that the data is going to be passed from the local machine to the redundant ones, we are vulnerable to errors in the transport process. However, the application of error detection and correction techniques present within the data link layer (layer 2 of the OSI model) of TCP-IP-based protocols would significantly mitigate possible errors in the transmission process. At the same time, an integrity check is crucial to reconstruct the files and, more importantly, to ensure security within the network, as malicious data can be traced to its origin in case of malicious or faulty file propagation.

To this point, even when we have split the files into several amounts of pieces, we are still revealing information about it (partially but still revealing it). No security measures have been applied.

B. CRYPTOGRAPHIC FUNDAMENTALS

To this extent, I think we were just expecting to be exchanging sensitive (and critical) information haphazardly along the network, but we need to think about the possibility of malicious actors paying special attention to our information traffic. Our final objective is to deploy a cyber defense tool that can correct successful attacks on our system, so preventing them should also be in our greatest interest. In this case, there exist different cryptographic strategies that we should be taking a more practical look at.

1) SYMMETRIC ENCRYPTION ALGORITHMS

As presented in Figure 2, we can see that symmetric encryption requires the possession of the secret key by the Sender as well as the Receiver. For this, previous knowledge of the secret key (commonly associated with a “password”) is necessary, making it impractical for cases where the key should be remotely distributed. Please note that if you implement password-based authentication, you should at least hash it to avoid revealing the information to anyone,

FIGURE 3. Asymmetric key-encryption scheme, where scenario 2 is only valid for the RSA algorithm.

or even better: a hash of a password plus some Salt [7] and Pepper (also called “secret salt”) [7], [8].

In our case, we have adopted the Advanced Encryption Standard (AES) Algorithm [9], also known as “Rijndael”, first proposed by Daemen and Rijmen [10]. This scheme represents a NIST (National Institute of Standards and Technology) norm for symmetrical encryptions. However, this is probably the most used cryptographic encryption for files and information, even when the key cannot be remotely distributed, due to its relatively good computational performance (about 11MiB/s for a 200 MHz processor from 2001 [11]) compared to any Asymmetric Encryption Scheme (RSA for a key length of 2048bits demonstrated an encryption rate of 306.4KiB/s for a 3.2GHz processor in 2007 [12]), while still preserving equal or even better security levels.

2) ASYMMETRIC ENCRYPTION ALGORITHMS

In comparison to Symmetric Encryption Algorithms, Asymmetric ones require two different keys for encryption and decryption. Due to the existence of two different keys, one for encryption and another for decryption, this algorithm requires the exchange of a key, making one disclosed or “public”, rebaptizing these algorithms as “public key cryptography”, where in all cases only the private key can generate a public key, hence the “uniqueness” that binds the private key to its owner’s identity (and now you might have come into realization about the fundamentals of cryptographic signatures). Moreover, anyone in possession of the private key can make a message public to the owners of the public one, while on the other hand (and more often used), anyone in possession of the public key can send an encrypted message that can only be decrypted by the owner of the private key [13], as shown in Figure 3. In our case, due to its practicality, simplicity, and libraries compatibility, we decided to use the Rivest-Shamir-Adleman (RSA) algorithm [14], which bases its complexity on the computation of high-value prime numbers.

FIGURE 4. Shamir’s secret share algorithm principles. Here we can see three key points necessary to reveal a secret.

At this point, the reader should know that there exist different types of asymmetric encryption algorithms, where the most common ones are the RSA, and the Elliptic-Curve Cryptographic (ECC) algorithms [15], [16], the later one recently more popular due to its improved performance compared against RSA, as the key length necessary for secure encryption and decryption increases over time. The “minimum secure key length” computational performance is now similar (i.e., 3072 bits for RSA and 128 bits for ECC), but soon ECC performance will significantly surpass RSA [17].

Nonetheless, due to the overall poor performance of all asymmetrical algorithms compared to symmetrical ones, we need to appeal to hybrid schemes, where we combine public key schemes to exchange the common key, making the communication channel secure for all the participants. The one used by us is the TLS (Transport Layer Security), very commonly used on HTTPS (where the last “s” is for secure), where we can exchange first the public keys within crypto-signed certificates and then the AES-based key for fast and secure communication. It is important to remark that we can make use of more elaborated TLS security schemes but considering the low amount of expected connections and compromise of the server’s secret key represents no threat to the client (for our study case).

To this point, the use of HTTPS in the exchange of packages would have been enough for creating secure channels for data exchange, but we will be using the different cryptographic algorithms presented in different orders to create a scheme for secure information storage and retrieval. To this extent none of the methods mentioned allow the federated exchange of keys to divide the power of the receiver machine.

3) SECRET SHARING ALGORITHM

A name we have mentioned before as one of the most prominent cryptographic mathematicians in the 20th century has been Adi Shamir, who, besides his contribution to the RSA encryption algorithm, also proposed a scheme to distribute several keys (points in a curve) so, their combination can lead

FIGURE 5. SHA-1 hash function applied to the input, with its respective hash.

to a common shared secret, as represented in Figure 4 [18]. This scheme is recommended for Threshold cryptography by the NIST 8214 standard [19], in combination with other standard schemes to ensure the secure distribution of keys. More in detail, this scheme uses polynomial interpolation to distribute the secret among the participants. For secret shared schemes, “n” points are distributed along “n” participants, where “m” threshold keys are necessary to reveal the secret.

Secret Shared schemes commonly make use of polynomial interpolation [18], a set of linear equations (Blakley’s secret sharing) [20], the Chinese Remainder theorem (Mignotte’s [21] and Asmuth-Bloom’s Secret Sharing [22]), or even homomorphic Encryption for Post-Quantum applications (Benaloh’s Secret Sharing [23]). Any of the aforementioned methods suffice and would be enough for our Proof of concept. Nonetheless, due to its simplicity and library availability, we have opted for a variation of the Protocol proposed by Krawczyk, known as “secret sharing made short” [24]. Plane Shamir’s secret share would require an important amount of storage space to apply it to a file directly. Instead, Krawczyk proposes very simple steps:

- 1) We Encrypt the file with a randomly generated key using a Symmetric Encryption algorithm.
- 2) Next, by the application of the IDA method, we Split the file into “n” different pieces with a threshold of “m” necessary pieces for reconstruction.
- 3) We implement Shamir’s secret to split the secret key into “n” different keys with a threshold of “m” minimum necessary keys.
- 4) We distribute the keys by making use of a secure channel.

As to the knowledge of the authors of this paper, we could not find a suitable and well-supported library for the implementation of step 2, so we modified step 2 by applying just “data replication” with a redundant factor equivalent to “n - m”, but the application of IDA is strongly recommended due to its Fault-Tolerant and Storage-Efficiency advantages.

4) DATA INTEGRITY VERIFICATION: HASHING ALGORITHM

To this extent, anyone with a basic knowledge of blockchain would know already what a hash function is. As shown in Figure 5, a hash is the fixed data length output of a one-way cryptographic function (known as a hashing function) [7].

Considering the hash length “h” (e.g. 128 bits, 256 bits, 512 bits, etc.), every input value of any length will be associated with a unique fixed-length output value, which can be any one of the 2^h possible ones (e.g. 2128, 2256, or 2512,

FIGURE 6. Virtual machine technology (left) compared to container technology (right).

or if we just place these as base-10 numbers, we would be speaking about 1038.5, 1077 and 10154 respectively, i.e. 54 orders of magnitude bigger than a googol [25]). In other words, these associations can be used to individually and uniquely identify the given input data to an output data identifier (i.e. hash) with an absurdly low probability of crashes (virtually zero), which is how the event of having two equal hashes with different inputs are denominated. On the other hand, given it is a one-way function, the only possible way of maintaining the same output while modifying the input is to try by brute force every possible combination until we get the same output, a task that would make Sisyphus himself feel lucky.

At this point, we can see that this method can be used to prove some knowledge without revealing the data (known as “zero-knowledge proof”, by comparing two hashes from different machines), or to prove that certain data remained unmodified after receiving it from any other actor, known as “proof of integrity” or “checksum” for the case of a file, as defined in the equation (2). Finally, if the hash is also encrypted with a private key, with the possession of the public key we can prove that certain data was unmodified and is associated with a specific private-key owner, basically a “crypto-signature” of the data.

$$\text{Hash}(X) = \text{Hash}(X') \rightarrow X = X' \quad (2)$$

C. SANDBOX ENVIRONMENT

A Sandbox is an isolated environment to confine software for security reasons, for it to run without affecting the rest of the applications, platforms, or overall system (i.e. hardware or other software) [26]. As our main focus is to improve the overall security of the whole network, the fact of receiving files and running them without hesitation represents a naïve approach, when we might be dealing with malicious software from the first moment, we get in contact with it.

This solution we propose is by making use of containers (which represent already isolated environments) with enhanced isolation for security [27]. The particular choice of docker allows the virtualization of the migrated application to be run within the host machine in a more general way without depending on hardware-specific or software-specific solutions while paying attention to the security of the receiving end. On the other hand, we require not

FIGURE 7. Verifiable computing by process replication.

one, but two layers of solutions, as the receiving end might be receiving a generic file looking to exploit security breaches. As shown in Figure 6, we might apply a Virtual Machine for hosting the Virtual Redundancy service (which also isolates the host machine’s OS at the cost of small overhead, compared to containers) or another container to run the migrated application (in our case, Sysbox, for “nested” container solutions [28], now acquired by Docker for Business solutions [27]), in between other less popular isolation and virtualization solutions. This architecture for hosting the applications is intended to ensure security from the host’s perspective, as the received file will have to be deployed as “Docker-In-Docker” within Sysbox, so, in case the deployed file contains or “is” by itself a malware, it will remain isolated from the rest of the machine.

D. VERIFIABLE COMPUTATION: VERIFICATION BY REPLICATION

While the last solution was presented to avoid malicious software affecting the host machine, we have no methods to be sure that the new host machine is running the algorithm provided by the original machine, or is just providing us with unuseful, malicious, or even dangerous data.

To check the computation, we can apply a simple method to probabilistically check for truth in the process: we can provide “N” independent machines with the same input and expect the same output from all of them. If the majority of values, more than a threshold “M” coincide, then we can say we “probably” have the true output in our hands [29]. As shown in Figure 7, this method does not necessarily require consensus, as the machines do not need to interact with each other, but it requires an external verifier (as the original machine is expected to fail). This means that the application would require a minimum of three machines for “value certainty” (i.e., two hosts, and one verifier running a “lightweight” program for comparing the results) or four machines (i.e., with three hosts and one verifier) to resolve in case of values mismatch. This method should be reserved only for very critical operations necessary within the system, as we are unnecessarily adding more processing burden to implement it.

E. PREVIOUS WORK

As shown in Figure 1, the main idea behind the Virtual Redundancy, as opposed to the conventional redundancy concept where dedicated hardware is applied for redundant operation, is to make use of the idle hardware resources of

FIGURE 8. Algorithm representation for optimal machine selection with multiple requirements vs. multiple capabilities criteria.

machines dedicated to other tasks within the network in order to enhance the resiliency, especially (but not limited to) the critical infrastructure as for the case of automation services in power distribution networks. In [2] (and summarized in [30]), the main idea is to make use of the distributed nature of Blockchain networks to register the resources present within the network and coordinate the migration of the service previous to failure. For this, the virtualization of resources is essential, as the idea is to be able to reproduce the same behavior and responses as the system previous to migration as is the case for sensors and actuators, which should be “virtually rewired” to the new processing location by redirecting the communication flow, not to mention that the new host should also be capable of running the migrated algorithms, so the more generic the software and hardware resources and standard resources, the better.

Leaving now behind the necessary assumptions for its implementation, we need to quickly describe how the selection process of the new host is carried over without including the mathematical details for brevity reasons (nonetheless inviting the reader to check them within the associated publications provided as part of the cited literature in [2] and summarized in [30]). So, prior to machine (and resources) registration, the smart contract gathers the application computational requirements to filter all machines with fewer resources than required and then proceeds with the application of the Analytical Hierarchical Process (see [31]). Finally, the TOPSIS algorithm [32] points out a list of possible machines able to receive the algorithm, from the optimal one to the one that would suit the worst applicable case (but still suitable to receive the migration), as shown in Figure 8.

Once the optimal host has been identified in between all the machines registered within the blockchain network, the local machine and the new receiver are bound by a Smart Contract that starts the preparations for the eventual failure (by the use of CALVIN IoT [33]). To exemplify the solution, in [30] a power distribution network divided into three different automation areas has been proposed, as shown in Figure 9.

FIGURE 9. Example of power distribution grid divided into three different control and automation areas (controlled by Substation automation Units A, B, and C), as presented in [30].

FIGURE 10. Failure of one of the SAU “C”, leaving Area “C” without automation services, as presented in [30].

In the eventual case of failure of one of the Substation Automation Units (SAU), due to the lack of redundant devices, we might not only lose the ability to control or protect the different elements present within Area C but rather the whole operation of infrastructure, leading to blackouts (see [1]) that might lead to possible human as well as material losses as shown in Figure 10.

These scenarios are more than common due to the lack of redundant devices to support the operation in the event of faults, proper of the power distribution network architecture.

Nonetheless, in the case of resources virtualization and migration performed previous to the failure, the service restoration can be performed by migrating the critical services present within SAU “C” into any other SAU (to SAU “A” in the case presented in Figure 11).

Now, both areas are under the control of one SAU by the use of idle resources. Finally, even when the migration is performed on virtual elements, the automation operation to control area C is expected to be resumed as soon as the heartbeat of “C” is no longer perceived within the network. In summary, the solution proposed in [2] contemplates the following operations within the blockchain:

- Node registration
- Register Node Computational Resources

- Upload Application Computational Requirements
- Perform the request for Optimal Node migration
- Perform the Application Allocation
- Computational Resources Update
- Node Deletion

Out of the blockchain the whole migration, as already mentioned, is orchestrated by CALVIN IoT, which serves as the application runtime manager, and Node-Red [34], an event-driven API for wiring applications, online services, and other APIs. Leaving aside the fact one is deprecated, and the other presents a processing load that leads us to rethink its need, the current solutions are not prepared to tackle possible security problems that might come along with the solution, information leaks, malware propagation, and man-in-the-middle threats.

III. METHODOLOGY

A federation in computing is a group of systems that maintain their autonomy but agree to share resources to achieve a shared objective. In this section, we will see how the different technologies recently described can help us in the coordinated effort to provide virtual redundancy without losing sight of the decision-making power that each member has to maintain a reliable and secure system.

FIGURE 11. Restoration of “SAU C” critical services by migration into “SAU A”, as presented in [30].

As discussed in the previous sections, we applied the permissioned Blockchain architecture with Hyperledger Fabric and Smart Contracts for Virtual Redundancy as presented in [2], while our main contribution lies especially in replacing the application and API components, with a PoC application designed with the security fundamentals in mind, which we baptized as “Last Will Letter” (LWL), as the whole scheme was inspired on the fictional ritual for power transition within a secret society to name a new successor upon the decease of its grandmaster. As a consequence, using a permissioned blockchain allows us to enforce access control and ensures that only authorized nodes participate in the network, enhancing security pursuant to our threat model.

A. ACTORS AND COMPONENT DESCRIPTION

From here, we need to present the different roles necessary for our solution and its relevant components, while a detailed description of each one of these is presented in the following subsections.

1) TESTATOR

A Testator is a node responsible for requesting the service to the smart contract, as well as preparing and distributing a specific asset between its different Executors.

Figure 12 depicts the Testator’s functions within the closed box. In case the Testator fails, the asset once executed by

FIGURE 12. Testator role for the LWL algorithm implementation.

FOR REDUNDANT OPERATION: Redundant Inheritors or Redundant Inheritors with replication-based validated computing

FIGURE 13. Inheritor role and operation modes for the LWL algorithm implementation.

it will be migrated to an Inheritor node, which will become this asset’s new owner. The decision power is centered on the Testator.

2) ASSET

The asset is the program or data to be migrated to its new successor.

3) INHERITOR

The Inheritor is represented as the blue box in Figure 13. An Inheritor is a node chosen by the TOPSIS algorithm to be the next host of a migrated asset. After receiving and deploying an asset, the Inheritor becomes the Testator for that asset.

As shown in Figure 13, there can be more than one possible inheritor, in case of redundant inheritors or for verifiable computation purposes for very critical applications.

4) TESTAMENT

A Testament is a file containing instructions on getting access to the asset content. The data stored in the Testament is composed by:

- Instructions on how to reassemble the divided encrypted asset (hashes and order of the files)
- Instructions on the migration period of the asset (in case the migration is going to be periodical)
- Instructions on how many “generations” should receive the asset in a period (to avoid passing a cursed asset that provokes the failure on the host)
- The encryption key of the asset

The Testament is created and encrypted by the Testator and stored by the Inheritor.

5) EXECUTOR

Executors are nodes are the red nodes depicted in Figure 14 responsible for receiving and storing a piece of the encrypted asset, as well as one of the secret keys necessary for

FOR REDUNDANT OPERATION: Redundant Copies of the Asset

FIGURE 14. Executor role and operation modes for the LWL algorithm implementation.

FIGURE 15. Actor role definition stage.

the Testament execution. Also, and most importantly, the Executors are also responsible for deciding whether the Testator has failed or not, to initiate the Testament's execution, where the Testator is considered down in case more than half of the Executors agree on the absence of its heartbeat.

B. NETWORK DESCRIPTION

The manager application is the software responsible for executing the system workflow according to the nodes' roles, as received from the Smart Contract. In Figure 15, we can see the main possible routines of the manager application: once it receives the node's role for input, it proceeds to call a specific routine according to it.

C. TESTATOR'S FUNCTION DESCRIPTION

As introduced in Figure 15, the testator function has to prepare the asset for secure migration, as well as the testament. For this, as shown in Figure 16, the Testator should process the asset first by:

- 1) Symmetrically encrypting the asset (with the AES-256 algorithm).
- 2) Splitting the asset in "m" pieces.
- 3) Creating the Reassembly Instructions (i.e. pieces names and orders, checksum of pieces, etc.).
- 4) Creating the Testament (Merging the Symmetric Key from step 1 and Reassembly instructions in a file).
- 5) Encrypting the Testament (with Shamir's Secret Share algorithm).

FIGURE 16. Testament creation for inheritors and encrypted pieces for the executors.

- 6) Generating $m \cdot r$ secret keys, with a threshold greater than half of the generated keys.

After the whole process is finished, the Testator transmits the asset pieces and keys to every executor by making use of the TLS protocol, as presented in the previous section. It is important to add that, even when no copies are created, "r" copies of every piece are provided, being "r" the redundant value for our system (e.g., $r=2$ for two copies of every piece, or $r=3$ for three copies of each piece sent).

Finally, the Testator distributes copies of the Testament, depending on the redundant value "r". As demonstrated in Figure 17, no actor has enough information to deploy the asset alone without a federated decision of the executors. Additionally, AES-256 is currently considered computationally secure because the best known attacks require computational resources beyond what is feasible with current technology [10]. Shamir's Secret Sharing is information-theoretically secure, meaning that an adversary with fewer than k shares gains no information about the secret. This property is proven based on the randomness of the coefficients in the polynomial used to generate the shares [18].

FIGURE 17. Demonstration that no inheritor nor executor has enough information to claim the asset alone without a federated decision of the network. In blue is the process of the data for executors, while in red is the for Inheritors. In black, the intermediate processes are shown.

It is recommended that the redundant value “r” to be not so small to provide the system with enough fault tolerance, while also not too big to saturate the storage resources of the system. A redundant value of two or three might be enough to ensure enough redundancy.

At the same time, the inheritors’ operation mode is recommended to be applied without verifiable computation as the application might be demanding in terms of processing speed and processing power, unless more “trust” is required in the service due to the possible presence of untrusted organizations within the network. In that case, it would be an assumption that might get in conflict with the fact of critical services being deployed within; in consequence, we assume some degree of trust, as a private consortium blockchain network.

Moreover, the overall algorithm for the Testator is presented in Algorithm 1.

As can be appreciated within Algorithm 1, once every Inheritor and Executor has received the data, the Testator

Algorithm 1 Algorithm Followed by the Testator Machine

Require: asset A, integer m, integer r, integer threshold
Ensure: Distributed encrypted asset pieces and testament shares

- 1: $K_{\text{sym}} \leftarrow \text{AES-256-KeyGen}()$
- 2: $A_{\text{enc}} \leftarrow \text{AES-256-Encrypt}(A, K_{\text{sym}})$
- 3: $\{P_1, \dots, P_m\} \leftarrow \text{Split}(A_{\text{enc}}, m)$
- 4: $R \leftarrow \text{CreateReassemblyInstructions}(\{P_1, \dots, P_m\})$
- 5: $T \leftarrow \text{CreateTestament}(K_{\text{sym}}, R)$
- 6: $\{S_1, \dots, S_{m \times r}\} \leftarrow \text{ShamirSecretShare}(T, m \times r, \text{threshold})$
- 7: **for** $i = 1$ to m **do**
- 8: $\{P_{i,1}, \dots, P_{i,r}\} \leftarrow \text{CreateRedundantCopies}(P_i, r)$
- 9: **end for**
- 10: **for** $i = 1$ to m **do**
- 11: **for** $j = 1$ to r **do**
- 12: Send $P_{i,j}$ to executor using TLS
- 13: **end for**
- 14: **end for**
- 15: **for** $k = 1$ to $m \times r$ **do**
- 16: Send S_k to executor using TLS
- 17: **end for**
- 18: **return** “Asset and testament securely distributed.”

FIGURE 18. Recommended software architecture for using the LWL algorithm.

starts streaming a Periodic Heartbeat to the Executors, and a small, encrypted Asset Status file to the Inheritors. The heartbeat’s message (a timestamp signed by the inheritor and sent by TLS) is meant to reset a Timeout timer within the Executors, which, in the event of Timeout, they proceed to initiate the Execution of the Testament, by providing the Inheritor(s) with the key and pieces to claim the asset. On the other hand, the Status file is a file provided by the program, which stores the current state of its variables, in case the asset requires them during its restart. If that is the case, the asset will be fed with the Status file, but it should be prepared to generate the status file, as well as prepared to be fed by it.

Algorithm 2 Algorithm Followed by the Inheritor Machine**Require:** Encrypted testament from testator, periodic status file**Ensure:** Restored and redeployed asset upon testator failure

```

1: Inheritor receives encrypted_testament from testator and securely stores it
2: while true do
3:   status_file ← receive_status_file() ▷ Periodic status update
4:   if status_file is valid and testator is up then
5:     continue ▷ No action required
6:   else if timeout occurs then
7:     Prepare to receive asset pieces and Shamir keys
8:     for each executor in executors_list do
9:       (piece, shamir_key) ← executor sends asset piece and key
10:      Store piece and shamir_key
11:    end for
12:    symmetric_key ← reconstruct_key(shamir_keys)
13:    testament ← decrypt(encrypted_testament, symmetric_key)
14:    for each piece in asset_pieces do
15:      if checksum(piece) ≠ expected_checksum(piece) then
16:        return error “Integrity check failed”
17:      end if
18:    end for
19:    encrypted_asset ← merge_asset_pieces(asset_pieces)
20:    decrypted_asset ← decrypt(encrypted_asset, symmetric_key)
21:    Redeploy decrypted_asset to restore service
22:  end if
23: end while

```

Due to the possibility of migrating the status file containing the last state of the internal variables, the recommended software architecture to be adopted can be found in Figure 18, where state variables backup is recommended to be integrated within the asset’s software for a smooth migration, e.g. within Javascript Object Notation files (JSON). Also, when several instances of the same asset algorithm are needed, these can be distributed on different machines (for load balancing).

1) INHERITOR’S FUNCTION DESCRIPTION

Algorithm 2 depicts the workflow of the Inheritor routine. First, the Inheritor receives the encrypted Testament from the Testator and stores it between its local files. Next, the Inheritor receives periodically the Testator’s status file (encrypted with the asset’s key). In case the Testator is up, no action should be performed. In case of timeout, the inheritor prepares itself to receive the assets pieces and Shamir’s Secret Keys from the Executors, which will allow him to decrypt and read the Testament enabling him to check the checksum (to prove the piece’s integrity) and merge the

Algorithm 3 Algorithm Followed by the Executor Machine**Require:** Encrypted asset piece, Shamir’s secret key, heartbeat signal from Testator**Ensure:** Participation in asset migration upon Testator failure

```

1: Executor receives encrypted_asset_piece and shamir_key from Testator
2: Store encrypted_asset_piece and shamir_key in local files
3: Wait for start_heartbeat_signal from Testator
4: if start_heartbeat_signal is received then
5:   Start heartbeat timer
6:   while true do
7:     Query blockchain ledger for Testator’s heartbeat
8:     if Testator is up then
9:       Restart heartbeat timer
10:    else if heartbeat timer reaches timeout then
11:      Trigger asset migration
12:      Send shamir_key and encrypted_asset_piece to Inheritor
13:    break ▷ Exit loop after sending data
14:  end if
15: end while
16: end if

```

encrypted asset pieces- Once merged. Then, the encrypted asset is decrypted with the symmetric key also present within the Testament file, allowing it to redeploy the asset and continue providing the service.

2) EXECUTOR’S FUNCTION DESCRIPTION

Algorithm 3 depicts the workflow of the Executor routine. Analogous to the Inheritor, the Executor receives a piece of the encrypted asset and Shamir’s Secret Key from the Testator and stores them between its local files. Once the Testator distributes all the data necessary within the network, it sends everyone a signal telling them to start the heartbeat Timers. This signal allows the Executors to check for the heartbeats of the Testator, using a query in the blockchain ledger. In case the Executor detects that the Testator is up, the heartbeat timer is restarted. Otherwise, if the heartbeat timer reaches the Timeout, the asset migration is triggered to start the Testament’s Execution. In this case, the Executor sends its stored Shamir’s secret key to the Inheritor its piece of the encrypted asset.

3) IMPLEMENTATION

To test the Proof-Of-Concept, an application was developed in NodeJS containing the Management Application with every role programmed and ready. The selection of NodeJS was carried over due to its high availability in terms of cryptographic libraries (i.e., Crypto), as well as communication protocols (through express library), and easy maintenance of supported libraries. For the PoC,

FIGURE 19. Application isolation through the D-in-D approach.

FIGURE 20. Test network description with alpine Nginx [35] web service container for an asset of approximately 23.5MiB.

we propose a 5-node network, where each node is made by a Sysbox container, containing the Management application as well as the HyperledgerFabric’s peer running the TOPSIS Smartcontract, as shown in Figure 19.

More in detail, the node works in an Ubuntu image with Sysbox runtime, serving us as a sandbox environment for any routine executed within (including eventual malware), as these will be isolated to avoid any interaction with the host machine. Also, the containerized node has NodeJS natively installed, necessary for the execution of the management application software.

Moreover, as described previously, Sysbox allows us to safely execute the Docker framework internally, by configuring a Docker-in-Docker environment for the execution of the Hyperledger peer container to run a Peer of the blockchain network. This allows us to invoke the Smart Contract (named chaincode for Hyperledger Fabric blockchain framework), so we can make queries to the blockchain database (LevelDB) or to perform the migration decision function. Finally, the node also can deploy the asset container in case it is selected as the Inheritor of our system.

As shown in Figure 20, the most basic test scenario for our PoC requires a five-node network: one Testator (whose application is to be migrated), one Inheritor, and three Executors (to test the majority of decisions).

After the deployment of the 5 nodes, the blockchain system can be initiated, and in consequence, the Virtual Redundancy

Smart Contract can be executed, defining in this way every node’s role. At this point, we can start the testing and quantification of the LWL algorithm.

IV. VALIDATION AND RESULTS

In this section, we will present the report of the fundamental tested scenarios, as well as quantify the computational resources involved and times associated with the operation of the LWL algorithm. The test files containing the algorithm’s implementation and resources can be found available in [36].

A. SCENARIOS ANALYSIS

In this section, we will present the report of the fundamental tested scenarios, as well as quantify the computational resources involved and times associated with the operation of the LWL algorithm.

1) SHAMIR’S SECRET KEYS ARE LESS THAN HALF OF THE EXECUTORS

Given the case where, after the migration, the Inheritor receives less than half of Shamir’s secret keys from the Executors, the overall safety of the system is kept. In this scenario, the Inheritor was not able to reconstruct the Testament encryption key and open the Testament, making it virtually impossible to calculate the last key even in the eventual case of having all but one key necessary for the Testament execution. This also means that the Inheritor will not be capable of accessing the asset reconstruction instructions or the asset decryption key. In summary, in this case, the Inheritor (or any malicious actor) won’t be able to recover and redeploy the asset, since it was not authorized by more than half of the Executors.

This locking procedure ensures the safety of the system in case the Inheritor is attacked and becomes a malicious machine.

2) ONE EXECUTOR FAILS

In case one Executor fails the Inheritor will not receive the migration data stored by such Executor. This means that the Inheritor will not receive the asset pieces stored by the failed node. However, thanks to the redundant feature of the algorithm, the Inheritor receives the missing piece(s) from another Executor (which is still operational). In this way, even if one Executor fails, the Inheritor receives all the necessary encrypted asset pieces.

Apart from that, in case an Executor fails, such a node is not able to send its Shamir Secret key to the Inheritor. However, in this case, the Inheritor is still able to reconstruct the Testament key since to do that, it needs only more than half the number of created keys. In the scope of this simulation, the Inheritor obtains 2 out of 3 Shamir Secret keys and would still be able to reconstruct the Testament key.

Therefore, the conclusion is that, in case one Executor fails, the system still performs as expected, without harm.

TABLE 1. Execution environment.

Operating System	Ubuntu Linux 20.4.3 LTS (64-bit)
Memory	4.4 GiB
Processor	Inter Core i7-8550U -x86
Clock Rate	1.8 GHz

TABLE 2. Processing resources required by every node to execute the LWL algorithm.

Machine Role	Physical	Process Executed	Execution Time
Testator	11.85 MiB	Asset Encryption, Pieces Preparation, Testament Preparation	14.31s
Inheritor	11.65 MiB	Pieces Merge, Asset Description, Testament Decryption	10.43s
Executor	11 MiB	Pieces Transfer	4.67s

3) THE INHERITOR FAILS BEFORE THE TESTATOR FAILS

In the redundant operation mode scenario multiple Inheritor candidates are chosen after the execution of the TOPSIS algorithm. All the candidates receive from the Testator the encrypted asset and encrypted Testament. The machine with the best TOPSIS score is selected as the Inheritor, but the other candidates keep the asset and Testament stored until the asset migration is properly executed.

In case the chosen Inheritor machine fails before the Testator fails, a new selection of Inheritor is performed by the system, e.g., by selecting the second candidate machine provided by TOPSIS. Since such a machine already has the necessary files, the asset migration can be successfully executed.

B. COMPUTATIONAL RESOURCES MEASUREMENT

In order to quantify some of the variables, such as the computational load, we have reported the characteristics of the machine where the test was carried over in Table 1. In Table 2, we can find the RAM and Execution time of the different nodes simulated in the network presented in Figure 20 (with Alpine Nginx web service container for the asset, with a size of approximately 23.5MiB [35]).

The RAM field regards the dynamic memory used by the node to perform the manager application routines. The Executor consumes less memory, which could be explained by its function mostly related to communication and data transmission, relatively small in terms of computational load than in the Testator's and Inheritor's scenario. Apart from that, both the Testator and Inheritor perform many cryptographic operations, as well as file manipulation (reading – writing), which influence the routine's workload. The RAM utilization was measured with the nodeJS process memory usage utility within the container, while it is important to add that every container had a Virtual Memory assigned of 2GiB [37]. This assigned memory is dedicated to the container as the process is isolated from the rest of the memory of the host machine. The amount of virtual

memory assigned to the container can be reduced, but as this work didn't focus on resource optimization, further tests are required to determine the minimum Virtual Memory necessary for running the service. Also, it is important to consider that the memory consumed by the asset application should also be considered as it runs within another container.

Furthermore, the static memory used by the nodes to store the manager application files, such as the manager application, and all the attached modules (packages such as AES encryption, split-merge, etc.) is 438MiB, independent from the role or node, since they share the same files (as every node can eventually take any role). Additionally, the Docker image in charge of simulating every node in the network has a storage capacity requirement of 2.11GiB, which includes the operational system used (Ubuntu Focal distribution with Sysbox runtime) and all the packages related to Hyperledger Fabric (fabric-tools, fabric-peers, fabric-orderer).

Regarding the execution times reported in Table 2, it is to be expected that they will have a very diverse behavior when it comes to the roles of the nodes. The execution times presented are associated with the main process involved in every role's execution, hence, these are all different.

In this scenario, the manager application execution by the Testator is longer, since there is an encryption process required for the asset and Testament creation, as well as their distribution to the other nodes, e.g. the creation of the Testament by the Testator and its submission to the Inheritor. Similarly, the execution of the manager application by the Inheritor involves the reception of the files from the Executors and a significant decryption load associated with the testament and asset reconstruction process. Docker image redeploy has not been considered within the table, as it is a Docker-dependent time (in consequence, is independent of the proposed algorithm).

C. MALWARE PROPAGATION ANALYSIS

Malware file threats can be described as attempts to place malicious code within a file that might be shared and eventually executed. This type of threat is avoided in the algorithm proposed in this work since before executing the asset the Inheritor node is assured that the asset file is not corrupted. During the migration, the Inheritor receives pieces of the encrypted asset and a Testament with instructions on how to reconstruct the divided asset. More specifically, the Testament stores the hash of the content of each asset piece. The Inheritor uses the hashes of the asset pieces to reassemble the same encrypted asset that was sent by the Testator. In other words, since the hash values stored in the Testament are the same as the asset pieces' hashes stored by the Inheritor, it is possible to ensure that the encrypted asset sent by the Testator is the same as the reconstructed encrypted asset stored by the Inheritor. Therefore, the corrupted file threat is avoided.

Apart from this, the usage of Sysbox runtime in the nodes' implementation ensures that they cannot execute any code that would harm the host/physical parent machine. The nodes work in an isolated environment, meaning that all the

TABLE 3. List of high-level vulnerabilities previously found in sysbox's container (patched).

policykit-1/libpolkit-gobject-1-0 - Out-of-bounds Write	This could cause a local privilege escalation and give administrative rights to unprivileged users in the target machine.
OpenSSL - Buffer Overflow	Could alter the content of data held in the buffer, changing the behavior of applications.
OpenSSL - Infinite Loop	Could create an infinite loop that results in a denial-of-service attack.
expat/libexpat1 - Exposure of Resource to Wrong Sphere	Allows attackers to insert namespace-separator characters.
expat/libexpat1 - Improper Encoding or Escaping of Output	Lacks validations of encoding.
cyrus-sasl2/libsasl2-modules-db - SQL Injection	Passwords do not escape for a SQL insert or update.

executed routines (including eventual malware) are isolated and cannot interact with the host machine.

Nonetheless, the Sysbox image used for the LWL Algorithm was examined, to determine its vulnerabilities and the risks it could introduce to the program. To execute vulnerability scans we decided to apply Snyk [38], an automated vulnerability scanner that is integrated with Docker, simplifying in this way the process of scanning the whole container. It lists the vulnerabilities found and gives detailed information on the severity and which package creates it.

As Snyk provides a history of patched vulnerabilities, we found that Sysbox never presented critical ones, while all high-level vulnerabilities (see Table 3) have been fixed by the date of the present publication with updates on its packages.

D. MAN-IN-THE-MIDDLE THREATS

Man-in-the-middle (MITM) threats consist of a malicious node in the middle between two other actors. In consequence, this node has total control of the traffic between the input and the validator output, where the disruption of the traffic might be the most common, but the least of the problems, as a more intelligent approach would try to add noise or even fake a real processing output so, the client machine expecting the result from the middle process might produce erratic or even destructive effects. To overcome this type of attack coming from inside our network (and more specifically from the inheritor), proper verifiable computation techniques can be applied, so the real application of the migrated program can be checked once received.

To test this, we had to integrate the Verifiable Computation technique within the asset application, by the implementation of a consensus over the PMU Sensor Value with Bad Data Detection [39], summarized in Figure 21. The Verifiable computation technique can be envisioned from the very application design (as per the case of [39]), making the solution simpler, and declaring its implementation into the smart contract is necessary, so the migration is produced to more than one inheritor.

FIGURE 21. Verification by replication network tested.

It is important to add that the application of consensus is not necessary, but it increases the complexity, as a larger number of external parameters are involved, enhancing the effort necessary to attack the network and the identification of attackers. On the other hand, it exposes the identity of the other participants involved in the process, enabling possible collusion between actors.

In the test, the actuator received the consensus result of all the processing nodes and applied Triple Modular Redundancy (TMR) to their values, so, if two or more results match, the respective results are considered correct. Nonetheless, if only two inheritors work, the network is already vulnerable to MITM attacks by submission of very different values, causing both values to be rejected. Also, if only one inheritor is present, the value might be rejected as a lack of minimum valid voters. Due to this case, we applied some flexibility, requiring availability of service over consistency, as we needed to choose one over the other due to the restrictions imposed by the CAP theorem [40] (partition-tolerance is in our case impossible to discard). In this scenario, we chose to make two exceptions to the TMR:

- In case of only two nodes present and no consensus is reached, accept the value closer to the last consensual value reached.
- In case only one was present, we decided to accept the value anyway under the assumption that no other valid processing node was present to complete the consensus.

The application of TMR was also demonstrated to be handy at the time of detecting errors or faulty values from the processing nodes (which in our case were unintentionally present).

E. BRUTE FORCE ATTACKS

Brute force attacks are a straightforward but computationally intensive method of cryptographic attack since several attempts for guessing the passwords or encryption keys need to be carried out until the correct one is discovered. The attacks can be divided into simple Brute force attack where every combination is tested sequentially without any prior knowledge about the target's password characteristics, and dictionary attacks, which leverage pre-defined lists of common passwords or phrases to expedite the process. Therefore, the effectiveness and feasibility of brute force attacks depend significantly on factors such as computational power available to the attacker, optimizations like parallel processing across multiple machines, and countermeasures implemented

FIGURE 22. Scenario analysis for different attacks.

by systems. Despite their theoretical simplicity, successful brute force attacks against modern cryptographic standards remain highly improbable within realistic timeframes due to the amount of key spaces involved. Given that AES-256 has 2^{256} possible keys, the probability of successfully guessing the key through brute force is nearly zero unless an exceptionally large amount of computational power is applied over an exceedingly long time, this assuming the attacker has complete access to the files. The scenarios for the different attacks are discussed in Figure 22.

F. INSIDER ATTACKS

Insider attacks represent a significant threat to organizational security, arising from individuals who have access to sensitive data or are part of the systems. Common methodologies employed in insider attacks include data exfiltration where sensitive information is transferred outside the network; privilege escalation, which allows unauthorized access to critical areas of the network; social engineering tactics that deceive the other nodes in the networks into revealing confidential information; and sabotage aimed at damaging the network assets. In LWL algorithm, In this context, the probability that an insider cannot reconstruct the secret when they possess fewer than n shares is crucial to understand the effectiveness of the secret-sharing scheme. The probability that an insider cannot reconstruct the secret when they have less than t shares can be expressed as:

$P(\text{fail}) = C(n - k, t)$, where the binomial coefficient is defined as:

$C(n, k) = \frac{n!}{k!(n-k)!}$. This means that if an insider holds fewer than the threshold number of necessary shares (in this case less than three), they cannot reconstruct or access the sensitive information protected by Shamir's Secret Sharing.

V. CONCLUSION

The work introduced here, as a continuation of the research from Sadu et al. [2], suggests a novel approach to improve the reliability of any distributed system but oriented towards the needs of the power grid. The original solution proposes the creation of Redundancy through Virtualization by the use of Blockchain technology. Unfortunately, the local application layer and API proposed in were no longer suitable for future projects.

While maintaining the blockchain architecture and the optimal machine allocation algorithm, this work comes up with the main goal of developing a suitable P2P alternative to replacing the application layer and API, taking into consideration the need for improved security in the algorithm allocation process, with three different threats in mind: information leak, malicious files propagation (e.g. malware), and man-in-the-middle.

In order to tackle the aforementioned problems, a scheme involving three different types of nodes (Testator, Inheritor, and Executor), named Last Will Letter was proposed, inspired by the fictional ritual for power transition within a secret society to name a new successor upon the decease of its grandmaster.

The service requester plays the Testator's role, whose function is to prepare the asset for migration, making use of a scheme based on the protocol "Secret made short", proposed by Krawczyk. Nevertheless, the lack of proper libraries for the application of the IDA file partition algorithm required us to apply plane data replication, making Krawczyk's scheme slightly different, but still practical, as the Advanced Encryption Standard for Symmetrical Encryption and Shamir's Secret Share were available libraries for the scheme application. The second type of node, the Executor, is in charge of guarding the encrypted pieces and keys until the Testator's failure triggers the Testament's execution, by the provision of the pieces to the valid successor of the asset. Here, the third type of node, the Inheritor, is in charge of applying the inverse process for Asset reconstruction. It receives the pieces and Shamir's keys from the executors and, after a careful integrity verification of the pieces, the asset is reassembled, decrypted, and redeployed. For the last step, a Sandbox environment was proposed by the use of Sysbox's solution to protect the host machine from malware propagation.

Also, to avoid man-in-the-middle threats, the LWL algorithm allows the deployment of several Inheritors at the same time, for them to operate with Verification by Replication Strategies (e.g. by the use of consensus and Triple Modular Redundancy). Nonetheless, the implementation of the Verifiable computing technique should be integrated within the asset itself for solution customization reasons. In the simulation presented here, the algorithm worked successfully even after the introduction of some degrees of stress by single Executor or Inheritor failures, without harming the general application performance.

Finally, the execution times (for a 25MiB asset) demonstrated that the system can be operational in approximately 10s upon migration, showing in this way that the main purpose of Virtual Redundancy is achievable with a secure migration scheme.

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CESAR A. CAZAL (Graduate Student Member, IEEE) received the Engineering degree in electronics with a major in industry control from the Universidad Nacional de Asuncion, Paraguay, in 2016, and the M.Sc. degree in electrical engineering, information technology, and computer engineering with a major in power systems from RWTH Aachen University, Germany, in 2019, where he is currently pursuing the Ph.D. degree with the E.ON Energy Research Center, Institute for Automation of Complex Power Systems. His research interests include distributed automation, control, and monitoring of power distribution grids, with a special emphasis on distributed computing technologies. Also, synchronized measurement techniques play a major interest in between his research topics.

SU MON TUN (Graduate Student Member, IEEE) received the M.Eng. degree in electrical and computer engineering from the King Mongkut's University of Technology North Bangkok, Thailand, in 2024. She is currently pursuing the Ph.D. degree with the Institute for Automation of Complex Power Systems, RWTH Aachen University, Germany. Her research interests include semantic interoperability and cybersecurity in the energy domain.

is a Functional Safety Application Engineer with TTCControl, developing applications for off-road vehicles.

LEONARDO LEONZI D'ALESSANDRO received the Engineering degree in informatics from RWTH Aachen University, and the double master's degree from RWTH Aachen University and the University of Sao Paulo, Brazil, in 2022. During his time with the University of Sao Paulo, he was a Research Assistant in the field of data science, focusing on researching the effects of pollutants on the biodiversity of the Amazon Rainforest. Currently, he resides in Bolzano, Italy, where he

automation and advanced monitoring of active distribution systems.

FERDINANDA PONCI (Senior Member, IEEE) received the Ph.D. degree in electrical engineering from the Politecnico di Milano, Milan, Italy, in 2002. In 2003, she joined the Department of Electrical Engineering, University of South Carolina, Columbia, SC, USA, as an Assistant Professor, where she became an Associate Professor, in 2008. In 2009, she joined the E.ON Research Center, Institute for Automation of Complex Power Systems, RWTH Aachen University, Aachen, Germany, where she is currently a Professor of monitoring and distributed control for power systems. Her current research interests include

operating systems, cloud computing, and high-performance computing.

STEFAN LANKES received the Ph.D. degree from RWTH Aachen University, Germany. From 2007 to 2017, he was an Academic Counselor with the Chair for Operation Systems, RWTH Aachen University. Since 2017, he has been the Academic Director with the Institute for Automation of Complex Power Systems, RWTH Aachen University. His research interests include

Professor and then a Full Professor. Since 2008, he has been the Director of the E.ON Energy Research Center, Institute for Automation of Complex Power Systems, RWTH Aachen University, Aachen, Germany. He is the author or co-author of more than 300 peer-reviewed articles published in international journals and the proceedings of international conferences. He was a recipient of the 2017 IEEE Innovation in Societal Infrastructure Award. He is an Associate Editor of IEEE SYSTEMS JOURNAL and IEEE *Electrification Magazine*. He is an Editorial Board Member of *Sustainable Energy, Grids and Networks* (SEGAN) (Elsevier). He is the Founding Board Member of *Energy Informatics* (Springer).

ANTONELLO MONTI (Senior Member, IEEE) received the M.Sc. (summa cum laude) and Ph.D. degrees in electrical engineering from the Politecnico di Milano, Milan, Italy, in 1989 and 1994, respectively. He started his career with Ansaldo Industria, Genoa, Italy, and then moved to the Politecnico di Milano, in 1995, as an Assistant Professor. In 2000, he joined the Department of Electrical Engineering, University of South Carolina, Columbia, SC, USA, as an Associate

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